

BEHAVIOUR OF SINGLE ARAMID FIBRE-YARNS UNDER TRANSVERSE IMPACT

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Summary

The aramid fibres, "Kevlar 29 and 49"*, are noted for their high capacity to absorb energy. This is exploited in applications where they are utilised to contain impact at ballistic velocities. The present work has been concerned with developing a fundamental understanding of the behaviour of individual yarns subjected to transverse impact at velocities of up to 140 m/s. An experimental programme was designed to study the mode of deformation of the yarn and the data produced has been correlated with previous hypotheses and with a computer model. It was found that the tensile modulus of both fibres decreased at high strain rates. Energy absorption involved a complex interaction of longitudinal and transverse strain waves. Earlier models were too simplistic to account for the observed behaviour.

* "Kevlar" is the registered trade name of E.I. du Pont Nemours Inc. for their aramid fibres.

Introduction

"Kevlar 49" and "Kevlar 29" are aramid yarns which are widely used in applications where their toughness is exploited. The two yarns are similar chemically but the tensile modulus of "Kevlar 29" is lower than that of "Kevlar 49" and the strain at failure correspondingly higher in conventional tensile tests. The factors governing the yarns' behaviour under ballistic conditions are not yet fully understood. In order to contribute to such understanding the results of high-speed transverse impact tests on single yarns, carried out in an earlier research programme [1] have been compared with the predictions made by a computer modelling exercise. These results have also been compared with earlier models. One of the main difficulties in accurately modelling the behaviour of the "Kevlar" yarns is that their dynamic elastic properties are not accurately known. Abbott et al [2] from the results of high rate tensile tests has suggested that their elastic moduli are lower at high strain rates. This is contrary to the usual behaviour of textile fibres.

Experimental

In the earlier work [1,3] transverse impact tests were carried out on single yarns of both "Kevlar 49" and "Kevlar 29". Both yarns consisted of a nominal 1000 filaments of approximately 12 μm diameter, in the case of the "Kevlar 29", and 11.9 μm for the "Kevlar 49", which had been subjected to additional stretching during manufacture. The test specimen consisted of a 400 mm length of the yarn held vertically between steel supports under light tension. Steel cylinders weighing 1.1 g were fired from a 5.6 mm bore air rifle so as to strike the mid-point of the yarn, at right angles to the yarn axis. Incident velocities varied from 40 ms^{-1} to 140 ms^{-1} . In each test both incident and residual velocities were measured and the energy lost by the projectile was calculated.

A high speed photograph was taken of each test. Two examples, one of "Kevlar 49" and one of "Kevlar 29", are given in Figure 1. Each photograph shows six superimposed photographs of the yarn under transverse impact from a projectile travelling at 120 ms^{-1} . They were taken using a multiple flash technique. The interval between the frames in each of the photographs in Figure 1 is 50 μs . This interval could be varied from 20 μs to 200 μs to enable different interaction times to be monitored.

Computer Simulation

A computer simulation of the behaviour of a single filament under transverse impact has been written. It was based on a simple finite element model. The multi-filament "Kevlar" yarns were modelled as single filaments whose density and cross-sectional area were equivalent to those of the whole yarn. The basic data input were the incident velocity of the projectile and a tentative value of the Young's modulus of the yarn, which determines the velocity of the stress wave (eqn 1). Using Newton's laws of motion as the only assumptions, the strain profile in the yarn, the deformed shape of the yarn and both the kinetic energy and strain energy in the yarn, at various interaction times, were computed. The calculated deformed shape was then fitted to the observed profile (i.e. the photographs) by adjusting the value of Young's modulus used in the computation, since this was the principal unknown parameter.

Discussion

J.C. Smith and co-workers [4,5,6] proposed a model for the behaviour of a single filament under transverse impact. Upon impact a longitudinal

Figure 1 Two series of high-speed photographs taken of "Kevlar 29" (left) and "Kevlar 49" (right) yarns under transverse impact. The projectile was travelling at 120 ms^{-1} in both cases and the interval between the exposures was $50 \mu\text{s}$. The passage of the transverse wave front from the centre towards the upper support may be clearly seen.

Figure 2 Schematic representation of the strain distribution in a yarn under impact. The point of impact is the origin and the longitudinal wave has travelled 100 mm along the yarn. The broken line is the prediction from J.C. Smith (4) and the dots are from the finite element model. Both are in close agreement.

strain wave propagates in the yarn, travelling away from the point of impact in both directions, at a constant velocity, if the behaviour of the yarn is Hookean. The strain profile in one half of the yarn is as shown by the broken line in Figure 2.

The velocity of the longitudinal strain wave front, C , is given by:

$$C = \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho}} \quad \text{where } E = \text{Young's modulus} \quad \dots (1)$$

and $\rho = \text{density}$

The strain in the yarn, ϵ_c in Figure 2, was shown by Smith to be related to the incident velocity of the projectile, v , and the strain wave velocity, C , by:

$$v = C \sqrt{\epsilon(1 + \epsilon)} - (\sqrt{\epsilon(1 + \epsilon)} - \epsilon)^2 \quad \dots (2)$$

The dots on Figure 2 represent the results from the computer simulation. The "overshoot" in the strain close to the strain wave front is an inaccuracy inherent in the finite element methods. Apart from this the computer results agreed with J.C. Smith's equations in all cases.

The point of impact on the yarn moves transversely to the original yarn axis with the projectile and a triangular shape is formed, as may be seen in the photographs in Figure 1. This is generally known as the transverse wave. The velocity of the transverse wave front, i.e. the base point of the triangle, is related to the strain, ϵ , and the strain wave velocity, C . J.C. Smith showed that its initial velocity, U_1 , was given by:

$$U_1 = C [\sqrt{\epsilon(1 + \epsilon)} - \epsilon] \quad \dots (3)$$

The transverse wave velocity is much lower than the longitudinal, and is a function of the strain. The ratio U_1/C rises from 0.03 at a strain of 0.001 to 0.23 at a strain of 0.1.

The computer simulation was run a number of times with the input incident velocities corresponding to those of the experiments depicted by

Figure 3 Further illustration of Smith's model. In the upper diagram the wavefront is travelling towards the end of the yarn. In the middle it has reflected at the end support and is travelling back towards the point of impact. The lower sketch depicts a further reflection. There is an equal strain increment at each reflection.

the photographs, but a different value for the Young's modulus was used in each run. A print-out of the position of the yarn at similar times after impact to the those in the photographs was obtained, and by comparing these results with the photographs it was possible to obtain an extremely good match for both types of yarn. Consistent values for the Young's modulus, independent of the incident velocity of the projectile, were found for both "Kevlar 49" and "Kevlar 29". These were:

$$\text{"Kevlar 49"} : 96 \pm 8 \text{ GN m}^{-2}$$

$$\text{"Kevlar 29"} : 74 \pm 5 \text{ GN m}^{-2}$$

However, the moduli of these yarns measured in standard rate tensile tests were:

$$\text{"Kevlar 49"} : 132 \pm 3 \text{ GN m}^{-2}$$

$$\text{"Kevlar 29"} : \text{Non-Hookean, modulus increased with increasing strain, initial modulus } 71 \text{ GN m}^{-2}$$

Thus the modulus of "Kevlar 49", which appeared to remain Hookean at high strain rates, was substantially lower at ballistic strain rates than at slower strain rates. The behaviour of "Kevlar 29" was Hookean at ballistic rates, its modulus being similar to its initial modulus at slower strain rates. Abbott [2] also observed that the moduli of "Kevlar" yarns were lower in rapid tensile tests than in quasi-static tests. He did not carry out ballistic tests.

The strain wave continues to travel in the yarn as the interaction progresses, being reflected first at the fixed end of the yarn and subsequently at the point of impact with further reflections as time proceeds. Smith assumed that the strain wave was completely reflected each time so that the strain increased in steps of equal magnitude. Figure 3 shows the strain profile in the yarn at a number of times after impact which would result if these assumptions were correct. He also assumed that when the strain wave and the transverse wave met there was no effect on the intensity of the strain in the strain wave. If correct these

Figure 4 Diagrams showing the comparison between the measured and calculated extension of the yarn, showing how the fit was obtained by manipulating the value for E used in the computation.

assumptions would imply that the rate of change in length of the yarn would be uniform, i.e.

$$\text{rate of change in length} = \frac{\Delta l}{t} = C_{\epsilon}$$

The changes in length of the yarns in the photographs in Figure 1 are plotted against time after impact in Figure 4. Also shown on the graphs are the uniform change in length of the yarn predicted by Smith (solid line) and the change in length predicted by the computer model (points). Smith's prediction appears to be correct at the beginning of the interaction but the rate of change of length falls as the interaction proceeds. The results from the computer simulation matched the experimental results closely.

Lynch [7] carried out a similar computer simulation for nylon yarns. His results showed that when the strain wave met the transverse wave for the first time, following the former's first reflection at the end of the yarn, the strain fell. A reducing strain wave, or compressive wave, travelled in the opposite direction towards the fixed end of the yarn. The shapes of the

yarn predicted by Lynch's simulation agreed well with photographs he had taken of ballistic tests. He observed sharp discontinuities in the otherwise straight section of the transversely displaced yarn. Similar discontinuities have been observed in the photographs of "Kevlar" yarns. Lynch suggested that they marked the position of the strain wave front.

It was difficult to study these effects in "Kevlar" since the strains and deflections were small as a result of the high modulus. Small variations were frequently masked by the overshoot observed in the computer results. Hence an attempt was made to reproduce Lynch's results using suitable material properties in the computer simulation.

The behaviour of the yarn was considered in detail during the period when the strain wave front was within the transversely displaced section of the yarn. Calculated strain profiles and yarn profiles at 10 μ s intervals during this period were produced. The results are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5a shows that the strain in the strain wave was indeed reduced when it met the transverse wave. The compressive wave travelling in the opposite direction is also evident. The two waves travelled at the original velocity and were both reflected at the ends of the yarn and at the projectile. The reduction in the strain arose as a result of the transfer of energy from strain energy to kinetic energy of the yarn particles. Thus J.C. Smith's assumptions cease to be valid when the strain wave meets the transverse wave for the first time. After this time his equations can be regarded only as an approximation. This reduction in the strain is responsible for the slackening in the rate of change of length of the yarn and the divergence from Smith's predictions.

The discontinuities observed by Lynch are visible in the yarn profiles in Figure 5b. They do not coincide with the position of the strain wave front. Comparison between the results in Figures 5a and b shows that the discontinuities do not correspond to any particular feature in the strain distribution. It was found that the discontinuity moved at the same speed as the transverse wave front relative to the unstrained yarn but in the opposite direction.

Craggs [8] suggested that when the strain wave met the transverse wave, part of each was transmitted and part reflected. He showed no experimental evidence but the evidence from the computer simulation appears to confirm his ideas. The fact that the yarn profile predicted by computing corresponds so closely to that observed in the photographs suggests that the predictions of the model are valid.

Energy in a single yarn under transverse impact

It was possible by means of the computer simulation to calculate the strain energy and the kinetic energy in the yarn at any specified time after impact. Figure 6 shows the energy partition for the yarn depicted in Figure 1a during the first 50 μ s after impact. The results were similar for the "Kevlar 29" yarns. As the strain wave travels away from the point of impact for the first time (the first 25 μ s in this case) particles behind the wavefront move towards the point of impact and therefore have longitudinal* (x) kinetic energy. Particles in the transversely displaced region move parallel to the projectile and have transverse (y) kinetic energy. The y-kinetic energy is twice as large as the x-kinetic energy

* The fibre axis is regarded as the x-axis even when the fibre is deformed. Measurements are made along the fibre, taking the point of impact as the origin.

5a

5b

Figure 5 In 5a the build up of strain after multiple reflections in a nylon yarn is modelled. In 5b the predicted shape of the deformed yarn is shown. The discontinuities in the yarn may be seen. This effect is more pronounced in the nylon than in the stiffer "Kevlar" yarns.

Figure 6 Shows the strain energy, kinetic energy and total energy stored in the "Kevlar 29" yarn depicted in figure 1 over a 50 μs interaction period. Initially the y-kinetic energy is dominant but later a 1:1 ratio is approached.

which, in turn, has the same magnitude as the strain energy. These ratios are independent of the incident velocity of the projectile. Thus, during this period the ratio, kinetic energy : strain energy is equal to 3.

When the strain wave front reaches the fixed end of the yarn it is reflected and travels back towards the point of impact. An equal and opposite velocity parallel to the yarn is imposed upon the yarn particles between the wavefront and the end of the yarn. These particles are therefore stationary (in the x direction). The x-kinetic energy is transformed to strain energy and as the wavefront approaches the point of impact the ratio, kinetic energy : strain energy approaches 1. During the whole of this period the force on the projectile remains constant so the total energy rises at a constant rate.

When the reflected strain wave front meets the transverse wave front the situation becomes more complicated. Equations for the energy distribution involve the length of the yarn as well as the material properties. As the interaction proceeds the ratio between the kinetic energy and the strain energy varies periodically - the period being the time taken for the longitudinal strain wave to travel along the yarn and back to point of impact one. The ratio finally steadies to a value of approximately 1.7.

Figure 7 shows the ratio between the kinetic energy and the strain energy for the two yarns, under impact at lower incident velocities. The

Figure 7 The kinetic:strain energy ratio for "Kevlar 29" and "49" yarns over a 400 μ s interaction period. After the initial fluctuation it stabilises at 1.7 until reflection of the transverse wave (see Figure 8).

ratio is initially very high in both cases. (This is not significant and is due to inadequacies of the finite element model at very short time intervals.) However it falls to 3 and then sharply to 1 as described above. It then rises to approximately 1.7 and initially perturbations about that value are evident. The curves are similar for the two yarns - "Kevlar 29" lagging slightly behind "Kevlar 49" as a result of its lower strain wave velocity, i.e. lower modulus.

The next major change in the energy position occurs when the transverse wave front is reflected at the end of the yarn. Figure 8 shows the two photographs corresponding to the two curves in Figure 7. The reflection of the transverse wave is visible in each photograph. After the reflection the ratio kinetic energy : strain energy falls sharply. The computed data showed that the kinetic energy fell and the strain energy rose sharply. The photographs in Figure 8 show that between the reflected transverse wave front and the end of the yarn there was very little transverse movement of the yarn. The kinetic energy is transformed to strain energy. J.C. Smith stated that a further strain wave was generated. The computer output showed a sharp rise in the strain close to the end of the yarn and it was also observed that many yarns failed shortly after this reflection occurred. At higher impact velocities failure took place before the transverse wave had reached the supports. This failure invariably occurred either at the supports or at the point of impact. This is consistent with the sudden increase in strain consequent upon reflection of the longitudinal wave.

Conclusions

It has been shown that under transverse impact from a projectile at incident velocities of up to 140 ms^{-1} both "Kevlar 29 and 49" behave in a Hookean manner. The apparent Young's modulus of the "Kevlar 49" is some 30% lower than that measured in low strain-rate tensile tests. That of the "Kevlar 29" was little changed from the initial modulus in tension. However, it was non-Hookean at low strain rates.

K 29

K 49

Figure 8 The two yarns depicted in Figure 7 showing the effects of reflection of the transverse wave at the yarn supports. This occurred approximately $300 \mu\text{s}$ after impact.

Energy is absorbed from the projectile as elastic strain-energy, and both longitudinal and transverse kinetic energy. The ratio of the kinetic to strain energy components change dramatically during the interaction period. This is due to the complex interactions between the longitudinal and transverse strain waves as they propagate along the yarn and are reflected from its ends. Initially the kinetic energy component is dominant, but it then settles down to a kinetic energy : strain energy ratio of about 1.7.

These interactions have been successfully modelled by using a finite element based computer program. The predictions of the model correspond well with the experimental observations. These suggest that although the previous models proposed appear to be realistic in the early stages of the interaction period, they are inaccurate at longer times.

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References

1. C.E. Morrison and W.H. Bowyer, "Factors affecting the ballistic impact resistance of Kevlar 49 and 29 Reinforced Composites", Fulmer Research Institute Report A91A/811 R903/2, November 1981.
2. N.J. Abbott, J.G. Donovan and M.M. Schoppee, "The effect of temperature and strain rate on the properties of Kevlar and P.B.I. yarns". AFML-TR-74-65 Part II, May 1974.
3. C.E. Morrison, "The mechanical response of an aramid textile yarn to ballistic impact", PhD Thesis, University of Surrey, UK 1984.
4. J.C. Smith, F.L. McCrackin and H.F. Schiefer, "Stress-strain relationships in yarns subjected to rapid impact loading, Part V, Wave propagation in long textile yarns impacted transversely". Textile Research Journal, April 1958, pp 288-302.
5. J.C. Smith, J.M. Blandford and H.F. Schiefer, "Stress-strain relationships in yarns subjected to rapid impact loading, Part VI, Velocities of strain waves resulting from impact". Textile Research Journal, October 1960, pp 752-760.
6. J.C. Smith, F.L. McCrackin, H.F. Schiefer, W.K. Stone and K.M. Towne, "Stress-strain relationships in yarns subjected to rapid impact loading, Part IV: Transverse impact tests". Textile Research Journal, Vol 26, No 11, pp 821-828, November 1956.
7. F. de S. Lynch, "Dynamic response of a constrained fibrous system subjected to transverse impact, Part II: A mechanical model". AMMRC TC70-16, July 1970.
8. J.W. Craggs, "Wave motion in plastic-elastic strings". Journal of the mechanics and physics of solids 1954, Vol 2, pp 286-295.